

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE FORMS OF SCIENTIFIC SEARCH AND CONSTRUCTION OF THE KNOWLEDGE IN THE HISTORICAL SCIENCE OF ANCIENT GREECE

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Abstract

The article deals with the process of formation of forms of scientific search and organisation of knowledge in the historical science of Ancient Greece. The main attention is paid to the study of essential differences between the ancient Greek historical science (Western cultural tradition) and the Eastern tradition of writing historical chronicles; the general cultural, world outlook and methodological foundations of scientific search, characteristic of this historical period, are revealed.

Keywords: historical science, Ancient Greece, foundations of scientific enquiry, worldview, methodology.

Documents are a necessary element in the structure of knowledge of many sciences (political science, sociology, psychology, etc.). However, for historical science they play a particularly significant role, as they are the most important (though not the only) component of its empirical foundations, and working with them is an essential component of the historian's identity as a scientist. Therefore, it is in historical science that the comprehension of the epistemological status of the document and the development of a methodology for working with it have not ceased since its inception and continue to the present day. The reason for this is not only and not so much the personal opinions of scientists, but a really complex epistemological problem. Since the concepts of "document", "historical document", and "historical fact" are among the fundamental ones for history, their definite interpretation immediately outlines the boundaries of the source material that can be used to build concepts and theories at a particular stage of the development of historical science. In fact, a particular system of historical knowledge grows out of the specific content of these concepts; they (concepts and system) condition each other. Therefore, the development of history as a science also meant a constant change, addition, transformation of the content of its basic concepts. We can say that the evolution of the concepts "document", "historical document", "historical fact" is one of the most important internal regularities of the development of history as a science.

Comprehension of the content of these concepts due to their significance for the structure of historical knowledge is a rather complex epistemological problem. For its epistemologically sound and logically consistent (at a particular stage of development of scientific knowledge in general and history in particular) solution, it is necessary to fix (explicitly or implicitly) the system of ontological, methodological, epistemological, logical and axiological foundations of science (7) as necessary preconditions. It is clear that a scientist-historian in the process of work does not necessarily consider a given cognitive situation in this form, but in

fact he solves it, based on his own worldview and methodological attitudes, formed in the concrete-historical conditions of his life. On the basis of a certain interpretation (explicit or implicit) of the above-mentioned bases of scientific research, three main cognitive processes are further realised:

1. the content of concepts is determined;
2. the methodology is developed for transforming the available initial content material into a "historical document", which is already a scientific fact, an element of the empirical basis of science;
3. the ways and methods of work of a scientist-historian with this scientific fact are described.

Different approaches to the solution of these problems determined in many respects the substantive specificity of different stages in the development of historical science, as well as the results of the work of its outstanding representatives. And their formation was conditioned both by the internal logic of the development of historical knowledge and by the whole system of socio-economic, political, cultural and scientific factors that emerged in a certain period. In this article we will try to reveal the process of formation and development of forms of scientific search and construction of knowledge in historical science, arising in the V century BC in Ancient Greece.

It should be noted that the accumulation of knowledge in various fields of science (mathematics, astronomy, zoology, botany, etc.) began long before this time. And in a number of branches the volume of accumulated knowledge was quite significant even from the point of view of a modern person. (Thus, Hammurabi's officials could solve biquadratic equations; in Assyria more than 800 species of animals and thousands of species of plants were described; names were given to the main constellations, which we still use today; the level of ancient Egyptian cosmetology was very high even by modern standards). However, this accumulated knowledge was chaotic. They were not systematised on the basis of unified principles. Therefore, they represented "rudiments of scientific knowledge" (sometimes the term "protoscience" is

used), which served as one of the gnoseological prerequisites for the emergence in the VI - V centuries BC of ancient Greek natural philosophy as the first form of scientific knowledge, which explained the world exclusively from natural causes, without reference to supernatural forces.

This general regularity in the development of human knowledge was fully manifested in relation to historical science. Historical knowledge in the form of chronicles, and quite numerous, existed outside Greece (Assyria, Babylon, Egypt) long before the 5th century B.C. However, this knowledge was impersonal, uniform, not systematised on the basis of some general principles. They could (later) be used in scientific works, but they were not scientific in themselves. As a result, history as a science also originated in ancient Greece - in Ionia, in the ancient Greek colonies on the coast of Asia Minor, which in their socio-economic development were far ahead of the development of similar polis on the territory of the Balkan Peninsula [1, p. 458]. Here a previously unknown form of historiography was formed, based on the world outlook and methodological attitudes already developed within the framework of natural philosophy [7, p. 19, 21]. Ionian philosophy (Miletian school (Thales, Anaximander, Anaximenes), Heraclitus, Eleatic school (Xenophanes, Parmenides, Zeno, Melissus) - the first form of natural philosophy - aims to characterise the Cosmos from the side of quality, to reveal its essential properties and show their manifestations in the processes of world change [5, p. 6 - 10]. And ancient Greek historians perceive and really creatively realise this general attitude in relation to society. As a result, within the framework and on the basis of the previously existing chaotic set of historical information, new bases of knowledge construction begin to form (with regard to the target settings of historical cognition, ways of knowledge acquisition, characteristics and forms of knowledge fixation, forms of scientific community functioning), which leads to its qualitative change; the first steps in the process of history formation as a science are made.

This "birth of history" is one of the most important parts of the process of formation of the European worldview on its way "from myth to logos" [12, p. 16 - 17 - 17] [12, p. 16 - 17], within the framework of which, about a century earlier, philosophy had already emerged, which began to explain the universe on the basis of purely natural causes, reason and logic.

At this stage, the primary conceptual apparatus of historical science begins to form. And in this case it also relies on the results already achieved in natural philosophy. In the development of philosophy from its origin in the 6th century B.C. to the beginning of the 5th century B.C. there was a qualitative worldview leap, a significant development of the conceptual apparatus. The initial transitional forms of knowledge fixation - "concept-image" - on the basis of which the philosophical "logos" was built, were replaced by full-fledged concepts formed purely rationally [3, p. 6-12]. The "logos" itself as a form of knowledge presentation was accepted by the emerging historical science [4, pp. 145 - 146; 9, p. 23]. The emerging ancient Greek historical prose (as a fundamentally new form of narrative construction in

comparison with the poetic one, describing mythological heroes and mythological events) took it as a given: its earliest works received this name, which meant "word", "story". In content, these early prose works were ethnographic chronicles describing the events that took place within certain localities [2, p. 5]. Herodotus significantly expands the content of this term, using it to denote both the whole of his "History" and its separate parts, possessing thematic unity [1, p. 458]. His "logos" told about reality, but this reality in practice also turned out to be mixed with mythical and simply fantastic details. In other words, it was a kind of transitional form from poetic figurative presentation to prosaic conceptual-rational one. This initial form of presentation of knowledge, based on a new approach to the description of events, on a new understanding of the essence and goals of such presentation, and, as a result, on new initial concepts laid in the foundations of historiography - determined both the fundamental difference of the emerging history as a science from the previous tradition of historical descriptions, and the directions of further development of ancient Greek historical science as a whole.

Ancient Eastern chronicles were mainly limited to the deeds of rulers and wars that took place (the number of killed opponents, captured prisoners, captured lands, the size of military booty). Ancient Greek historians fundamentally expand the object field of their science. Wars are certainly present in the narrative with necessity. However, in addition to them, historical works include geographical information, evidence about various peoples, their way of life, customs, fragments of mythology, etc. On this basis, a picture of a holistic, unified cosmos in its historical change is created.

The purpose of the ancient Eastern chronicler was to record the events that took place; he reflected the external, visible side of the historical process. And in this case the purpose of his work is considered to be achieved. For the ancient Greek historian it is only a beginning, a starting point, which is certainly necessary, but completely insufficient. His aim is to reveal the essence of what is going on, which may be hidden and which must be extracted in its numerous and seemingly unrelated manifestations. Clarity in understanding the goals and objectives of historical work, clarity in posing questions were one of the most important factors that allow us to characterise ancient Greek historiography as scientific [10, p. 31].

In the ancient historical chronicle, it is enough to record when and how events took place, which event followed which one. The question "why they happened" was outside the narrative. The course of events was taken for granted; everything goes as it should. On the contrary, in the ancient Greek historical tradition the question of causality follows with necessity from its general purpose setting [11, p. 345 - 346]. Greek historiography provides rationally justified answers to this question by referring to the available sources. Greek historians were aware of the need not only to describe the political events themselves, but also to identify the cause-and-effect relationships that permeate and organise these events [10, p. 32]. It is necessary not only to

describe the events, but also to clearly record and explain their explicit or hidden preconditions, motives, reasons, etc., as well. For this purpose it was necessary to subject the available factual material to rational comprehension. And all ancient Greek historians realise that this task is not less (and often more) important than a simple statement of events.

And the search for the causes of the events is not the only goal. The ancient Greek tradition is deeply humanistic; it endeavours to preserve the experience of previous generations for the generations to come. This attitude logically followed from the understanding of the flow of time as a cyclical process in which the same periods are repeated at certain intervals. In this respect, in ancient Greece history as a science was oriented not only in the past, but also in the future; it had practical value [9, p. 33 - 34]. Knowledge about the events of the past was useful because, according to the beliefs of ancient Greek historians, "events could repeat themselves". Greek historiography sought to preserve for mankind the valuable experience made, to teach people by the example of the past to anticipate the turn of events in the future [10, p. 32].

The realisation of such a goal required a special method of knowledge acquisition. The Eastern chronicler carefully, meticulously records event after event; he describes the process. The authors of ancient Greek ethnographic chronicles search, investigate, compare the evidence, logically verify it, etc.. And this way of acquiring knowledge gives a name to science itself. The term "history" was Ionian in origin [1, p. 499]. Its original meaning, as already noted, is "research", "enquiry", "investigation". For the first time in ancient and world literature in Homer's "Iliad" a certain "istor" (literally - "knowing, knowledgeable") is mentioned. There are disputes about who he was: a witness in court, an arbitrator, etc. In other words, initially "historians" had nothing to do with the description and study of the past, but acted in the sphere of legal proceedings. Later, the word "history" began to be attached to the works of chroniclers, which had a double meaning: "eyewitness testimony" and "investigation by interrogation" [2, p. 6]. [2, c. 6]. So, originally "history" was simply an investigation, and not only of the events that took place in human society, but also of the processes of nature (Aristotle's zoological treatise "History of Animals"; the work of his student Theophrastus on botany "History of Plants"; Pliny the Elder's encyclopedia (I century AD) - "Natural History") [11, p. 203 - 20 - 20]. [11, c. 203 - 204]. In other words, initially the term "history" did not imply anything "specifically historical", and only later it acquires the meaning of "historical research". A direct consequence of this approach was a critical attitude to the sources of information, which was also a significant difference between ancient Greek historiography and the historical tradition of the East and determined its scientific content [10, p. 32].

Another important difference between ancient Greek historical science and the previous tradition is the comprehension of the question of how the received and recorded knowledge about the historical process should relate to the process itself. And here, in full accordance with the methodological guidelines of natural

philosophy, the nascent ancient Greek historical science clearly singles out as a necessary, essential task the obtaining of true knowledge [11, p. 205]. In the preceding ancient Eastern tradition the question of truthfulness was not considered at all. But for Hellenic scholars it is an explicitly proclaimed goal, which initially determines the work of each ancient Greek historian. Moreover, this goal is realised not only in the form of some generally accepted, established writing practice. This approach is understood precisely as the primary methodology of historical research, which is clearly fixed by the authors explicitly in theoretical judgements of a general nature [11, p. 196]. To obtain such knowledge, various methods are used, which are clearly listed by each historian: criticism of predecessors, rational-critical comprehension of the obtained information [9, p. 34], comparison of different points of view, checking for logical contradictions, etc., as well as the following.

In ancient Greek historical science from the very beginning there is a process of working out the forms of knowledge fixation, which would allow to convey the content of the described events with the greatest reliability, accuracy and completeness. Initially, the rational processing of mythological narratives is carried out, and each author implements it not arbitrarily, at his own discretion, but on the basis of common specific principles [4, p. 104 - 107]; then eyewitness testimonies begin to be used, further - the available written documents and sources, etc. (in detail, the evolution of this component of the historical science). (it is advisable to consider the evolution of this component of ancient Greek historical science in more detail on the examples of specific personalities). In general, the general tendency consists in the constant and steady strengthening of the purely rational component in the cognitive constructions underlying the works of ancient Greek historians (it is necessary, in our opinion, to note a certain lag in the development of purely rational cognitive forms in historical research in comparison with natural philosophical [4, p. 115], which, however, naturally follows from the differences in the objects of research). Within two to three generations there is an obvious transition from descriptiveness and imagery to conceptual-rational comprehension of historical events [3, p. 103 - 112]. In the ancient Eastern historical tradition the above processes are absent; the form of knowledge fixation remained unchanged for centuries.

Finally, in Ancient Greece, for the first time in history, a social phenomenon emerges, which later received the name of "scientific community", primary forms of its construction and rules of functioning are developed. In the preceding period, its existence was simply impossible. Ancient Eastern chronicles are impersonal; their authors are unknown, as they did not mention themselves [11, p. 203]. They did not express any attitude to the described events. In Ancient Greece, the situation changes to a diametrically opposite one, laying the foundation for further cultural division of the West and the East: the culture of the Western type is "the culture of the author and authorship" [6, p.8] [6, c.8]. Ancient Greek historical works are immediately created as strictly individualised. Firstly, the historian's

own name is put in the very first phrases of the work. Everyone tries to record his own contribution to scientific knowledge, to demonstrate his originality. Secondly, the historian's task is clearly fixed: not just to recount certain events, but to describe what really happened, to write a true history. At the same time, the authors note the existence of their own subjectivity (the truth as it appears to them) and thus allow the existence of other points of view and the possibility of discussions between their representatives. Thirdly, there is always a critical attitude towards both predecessors and contemporaries: authors do not want to take for granted what is written by others. For them there is nothing obvious, nothing self-evident. They consciously reject tradition and consider it necessary to take a new look at what is already known [11, p. 196]. And this atmosphere in the "scientific community" was encouraged and actively supported by the existing social institutions and public opinion in ancient Greece: each significant polis considered it necessary to have "its" original philosopher, historian, rhetorician.

It is clear that the previously discussed differences between the historical traditions of the Ancient East and Ancient Greece are typological; they did not arise simultaneously, but were developed gradually. And in the work of specific ancient Greek historians they manifested themselves in different ways. However, this does not negate the general conclusion: despite the presence of rich traditions of historiography in the Ancient East, it is in Hellas that historical science in the proper sense of the word emerges.

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